

A Study on Impact of Disaster Management on Indian Economy

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Abstract

The role of emergency management falls under the jurisdiction of the National Disaster Management Authority of India, which is doing major work in mitigating the adverse effects of disasters and working through decentralized communities with a government-centric approach. Participation But when it comes to mitigating the large-scale damage caused by a disaster, it is necessary to consider strategic strategies and mitigation efforts. We have not been able to put in adequate rescue and rehabilitation efforts to deal effectively with the situation. A disaster is a severe disruption in the functioning of a population and society as a result of population or environmental damage that increases the ability of the affected population to be able to cope with their own resources.

Key words: Disaster management, Indian Economy, population, poverty, planning, decision making etc.

Introduction:

A disaster is a catastrophic situation that disrupts the normal way of life or ecosystem and requires extraordinary emergency interventions to preserve and protect life or the environment. India is the most disaster-prone zone in the world due to its unique geographic features and socio-economic conditions that expose people to frequent destruction due to hazards. Major hazards for India include major earthquakes, earthquakes, droughts, cyclones, floods, forest fires, fires, etc. Rapid growth in population has certainly increased the incidence of disasters. Natural disasters can be reduced but man-made disasters can be prevented to a certain extent. India has taken several steps and set up several institutions to reduce and mitigate the risks of disasters.

Problems of the Study:

Man-made disasters are also known as narrow emergencies such as disasters caused by major accidents such as fire, assault, looting and attacks, conflict situations and war. Disaster management is an ongoing process of reducing the impact of disasters. Disaster management strives for collective and coordinated efforts. In the event of a disaster, several activities must be undertaken. These include coordination, command and control, rapid damage assessment, power restoration, tele-communication and surface transportation, deployment of search and rescue operations, medical and para-medical teams, provision of drinking water and food items. Provision of temporary shelters, sanitation and hygiene identification and planning of resources, last but not least, maintenance of law and order are equally important.

Objectives of the Study:

Disaster management is a major problem in developing and agricultural nations like India. The main objective of this research is to study disaster management and environmental degradation

in India and some specific objectives are given below.

1. To Study the factors affecting on Disaster management.
2. To Study the environmental change and Disaster management.
3. To Study the various types of hazards and Disaster management.
4. To Study the Risk management and Disaster.

Significance of the Study:

India is a country prone to natural as well as man-made disasters due to geographical location, climate and social and economic conditions. About six percent of the total population is affected by various disasters every year. Whether a developed nation or a developing nation; When a natural calamity hits that nation, the nation suffers immeasurable losses. It affects the economy of that country. According to the different geographical conditions of the earth as well as climatic changes, different natural disasters such as floods, droughts, earthquakes, cyclones, landslides etc. occur in those regions. India is considered to be the most natural disaster prone country in the world.

Scope of the Study:

Precautions taken before an accident occurs are always beneficial. First aid is the first thing that comes to mind when you say accident. We all know that first aid is the simple measures taken to reduce the possible consequences of the injury or the risks arising from it before getting medical help in the event of an accident or accident. Like holding the injured body part under cold water to relieve the pain or using turmeric to stop the blood flow etc... In short, disaster management means reducing the damage as much as possible by studying the side effects of disasters at all levels such as loss of life, financial loss, and social loss. Various measures and measures planned to be taken.

Period of the Study:

While studying the disaster management in India and the factors that cause disasters and threats to human beings, the researcher has conducted member research by reviewing the information from 2022-23.

Limitation of the Study:

The key elements in the emergency planning cycle are prevention, relief, preparedness, disaster shock, response, recovery and recovery. All actions in the prevention component are directed towards avoiding these disasters. Also planning is done in the direction of how to minimize the consequences of a disaster. In a disaster, you risk death or bodily injury. You may also lose your home, property and community. Such stress puts you at risk of emotional and physical health problems. Post-disaster stress reactions resemble normal reactions seen after any type of trauma.

Research Methodology:

While studying the impact of disaster management on the natural environment and the various causes of disruption of human life, the researcher has used many secondary research methods. In this, member research has been completed analytically using a number of secondary researches such as research papers, articles, journals, newspapers, magazine, audio, videos, reference books, serial books, annual reports and library.

Research Method:

While studying disaster management and natural resources, researchers have used many secondary sources as well as conducted participant research using descriptive analysis method.

Results and Discussion:

Our country India is considered to be the largest natural disaster prone country in the world. Approximately 50% of India experiences earthquakes, 30% of droughts, and 10% of floods. Also, various types of communal riots, terrorism, fires are also seen happening frequently. Today we all feel blessed to blame the government when any kind of calamity happens. But if we start realizing our responsibility as citizens, things can change a lot. Natural disasters are usually a state of emergency because they require immediate intervention due to their high impact on human health and safety; they affect the normal functioning of operational infrastructure, disrupt normal day-to-day activities and pose a risk to residents and workers in the affected areas.

Disaster Management and International Approach:

Over the past two decades it has been recognized that natural disasters cannot achieve our sustainable development efforts. Hence, huge expenditure is required for disaster management all over the world. In the last twenty years, 1.35 million

people have died in natural disasters and 50 percent of them have died due to earthquakes. The rest of the deaths were due to natural calamities in the weather. Most of these deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries. Poor countries have paid a heavy price in human deaths. Even in developed countries the impact of natural calamities is not less. The reality of climate change is different and if we look at the calamities of the last fifty years, natural calamities have been created on a large scale, including earthquakes and storms.

Major three phases of Disaster Management:

1. Pre-Disaster Management:

This includes training, public awareness activities, practice and demonstration of systems, preparation of disaster management plan and maintenance of systems, liaison and coordination with various disaster response forces.

2. Disaster Management:

Planning and coordinating relief efforts in the event of an actual emergency.

3. Post-Disaster Management:

Controlling the post-disaster relief work, proper implementation of relief and rehabilitation plan etc.

Natural Disaster:

Natural calamities such as earthquakes, volcanoes, storms, floods, cloudbursts make people weak enough. You have to be constantly alert for that. Specially trained people have to be prepared to deal with these disasters. Internationally, the second Wednesday of October is reserved for this and the activities to be done to curb these disasters are reviewed. Many people around the world have lost their homes due to natural disasters. Lives are lost. Due to some disasters, the economic backbone of the countries has been broken. For this, the United Nations strongly realized that people should be educated about this disaster, information should be exchanged, and training should be given to face these situations. For this purpose, the emblem created by the Commonwealth shows the disaster-stricken countries of the earth and the branches of the olive tree surrounding them as symbols of peace. The purpose of this day is to instill a sense of security among the common people, to get immediate financial and medical help to the disaster victims, and to manage properly during the disaster.

Poverty and Disaster:

Unfortunately, the poor people of the world are the sure victims of this natural disaster. Recent tsunamis, volcanoes, earthquakes are recent examples of this. In order to create awareness about this day, the governments of the country and the country hold the hands of the media and issue an announcement and explain the rationale to the public.

Disaster Management and Public Participation:

There are two types of disaster which are manmade and natural disaster. Especially when natural disasters occur suddenly due to climate change. Therefore, the possibility of loss of life and money in such a natural disaster cannot be ruled out. We also see in daily life if a vehicle meets with a major accident or a person is injured in an accident, many people in the society rush to treat them and save their lives. Overall, this positive action is done by the society itself due to human sensibility and proper attention is also taken by the administration that is why the relationship between disaster management and people's participation is very close.

Development and Disaster Management:

Local level is also important in disaster management. Therefore, it becomes necessary to form various groups. On behalf of the District Disaster Management Authority, activities such as preparing the District Disaster Plan, updating it, organizing various workshops and color rehearsals are implemented in the district level program. Training of members of village disaster management committee, training of office staff, staff of voluntary organizations and public awareness through street plays, graffiti, billboards, poster competition, etc. programs to increase public participation.

Need for disaster management at local level:

Initially, the villagers have to be bravely prepared to face the flood or other natural calamities coming to the village. There is a need for management at the local level to increase the morale of the citizens. In order to deal with regular disasters every year, to deal with sudden disasters, to prevent damage due to ignorance and lack of information, to ensure minimum loss of lives and finances, to protect the vulnerable sections, to ensure that daily life is not destroyed after a disaster. Water supply, animal fodder, catering system, medical services, medical supplies, sewage system etc. will be run smoothly during the disaster period as well as after the disaster, especially minor children, old people, women and the disabled. Disaster management at the local level is necessary to ensure this. For that, it is necessary to get people's participation equally spontaneously.

Remedial plan:

The administration is ready to handle any possible situation that may arise. Apart from this, necessary instructions have been given to the health system to control the epidemics due to flood situation, the Mahadistribution Company to maintain the electricity supply, the telecommunications department to maintain the telephone service in good condition, the public works department, the state transport corporation, the irrigation department and other related

departments to ensure that the roads are connected to the traffic. Disaster Management means Disaster Management. This is a very big and broad topic. If you search the internet on this subject, you will find numerous books, articles and websites. It is impossible to take a comprehensive review of all this. However, we can definitely try to get the necessary information in practice so that we can try to save our lives by taking a path in a dire situation like a disaster.

Conclusion:

Disaster management has gained importance in recent times. To effectively handle any unexpected situation, we must be equipped with the latest technology. It cannot prevent the outbreak of disaster, but it can greatly reduce its impact. Earthquakes, floods, cyclones and heavy rains are all natural disasters. Disaster Management Authority has been established at divisional and district level under Maharashtra Disaster Risk Management to prevent loss of life and financial loss in such disasters. Not only this, the central government has passed the Disaster Management Act in 2005. Its basic purpose is to prevent losses in natural calamities and provide safety to all. Although this program is implemented by the administrative machinery, public participation is equally important to combat the crisis situation. The Departmental Disaster Management Authority is coordinating with the District Disaster Management Authority under the guidance of Divisional Commissioner Ganesh Thakur and what measures are being taken as per the plan from the district level to the village level in order to maintain a security system in the pre-monsoon as well as the monsoon season.

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